

Behavior of a low-temperature electrolysis technologies under intermittent operation: analysis of the impacts and mitigation strategies

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Introduction

In recent years, the incorporation of renewable energies into electrolysis systems has been attracting increasing attention from both the scientific community and major industrial stakeholders. This growing interest arises from their critical role in facilitating the shift towards low-carbon and sustainable hydrogen production. Nevertheless, the intermittent nature of renewable energy sources introduces complexity into this integration, affecting various key performance indicators of electrolysis systems [1]. Despite the significant lack of research in this area, especially at industrial scales, there is a prevailing literature consensus that intermittency exerts a substantial impact on the performance of electrolyzers across all levels of system operation [2]–[4]. The analysis and optimization of such intermittent operation are therefore critical steps towards a deeper understanding of the challenges linked to the integration of renewable energies as power sources for electrolysis systems.

This work focuses on the development of tools based on experimental work and modeling to achieve a twofold objective of gaining further insight into the impacts of intermittency on the performance of a 55 kW proton exchange membrane (PEM) electrolyzer and proposing solutions for their mitigation.

Methodology

A test campaign was conducted on a 55 kW PEM electrolyzer to gather preliminary information about the actual system performance when operating under intermittent conditions. In addition, a 0D performance model has been developed in order to simulate its operation of under various load scenarios. Simulation results have been fitted to the experimental polarization curve recorded from the electrolyzer plant. This preliminary step towards model validation is presented in this paper.

1. Experimental tests

The experimental tests were performed on a 55 kW PEM electrolyzer manufactured by ELOGEN. The system consists of a single cylindrical stack made of 48 cells, 600 cm² each, connected in series using bipolar plates. The plant is able to produce 10 Nm³/h of hydrogen at a nominal current density of 0.8 A/cm² and can operate at partial loads ranging from 10% to 100% of its nominal capacity. The Balance-of-Plant (BoP) is divided into two primary areas. The process area is equipped with a multitude of components including purification, cooling

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and conditioning units. In this section, an array of regulation loops and sensors is integrated to control the main operation parameters such as temperature, pressure, liquid levels, and gas composition, and to ensure safe operations. Additionally, a utilities area dedicated to electrical units, most notably the AC/DC rectifier, which plays a crucial role in electrical distribution and system power management, is integrated to the system. This area also houses water purification and cooling units. Figure 1 provides an overview of the process flow diagram of the electrolyzer.

Figure 1: Simplified Process Flow Diagram (PFD) of the electrolyzer

Specifications	ELYTE10
Nominal power (kW)	55
Nominal H ₂ flow rate (Nm ³ /h)	10
Load range (%)	10 – 100
Max ramp-up (A/s)	10
Stack specific consumption (kWh/Nm ³ H ₂)	4.3
System specific consumption (kWh/Nm ³ H ₂)	5.4
Nominal temperature (°C)	63 – 66
H ₂ pressure (bar)	30

Table 1: Electrolyzer manufacturer specifications (model ELYTE10 from ELOGEN)

The objectives of the test campaign were twofold. The first one was to establish a solid experimental database regarding the electrolyzer performance under nominal conditions ($P=55$ kW, $T=65^{\circ}\text{C}$). This dataset serves a dual purpose: as a benchmark for comparison with other tests and as a means to validate a performance model. The second objective was to test various types of dynamic power profiles based on grid services and renewable energies, in order to quantify the impacts of intermittency on the most relevant performance indicators of the system.

2. Modeling

A lumped and homogeneous 0D approach has been adopted to develop a multiphysic model of the PEM electrolyzer. The main model specificity lies on its ability to estimate the electrolyzer performance and behavior across diverse load scenarios, thereby promoting the incorporation

of renewable and intermittent energy sources, and its scalability to larger-scale electrolyzers. A semi-empirical approach, mostly based on analytical equations and existing works [4]–[7] has been applied to describe the physical behavior of the electrolyzer. At the system level, all Balance-of-Plant components including control loops have been designed in accordance with the manufacturer specifications. At a lower level, three submodels have been developed to capture the fluidic, electrochemical and thermal behavior of the stack. Figure 2 offers a deeper insight into the model structure, the input and output flows of each block, and how they interact with each other.

Figure 2: Model Flow Diagram (MFD)

The main assumptions are detailed below:

- Pressure drops are assumed to be low enough to be neglected;
- Temperature distribution is assumed to be uniform within the stack;
- Mass transfers and electrochemical and thermal behavior are assumed to be similar in each cell;
- Diffusion overpotentials are considered negligible at high current densities;
- Two-phase flow issues related to bubble coverage are neglected for the two following reasons: (i) they mainly impact performances at high current densities, (ii) the accurate description of such two-phase issues requires to take into account both time and spatial variations;
- The electrical dynamics of the system are considered to be fast enough to not be taken into account.

Results and discussion

1. Model validation

The analytical equation employed to model the polarization curve has been fitted based on the experimental data recorded from the 55 kW PEM electrolyzer. During this test, the electrolyzer started to operate from a cold state and a constant DC power setpoint was applied at the system

maximum capacity. As depicted in Figure 3, the temperature began to stabilize at $65^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$, approximately 1h after the Beginning-of-Test (BoT). Once thermal equilibrium was achieved, (j,U) data points between 30% and 100% of the system nominal power condition were collected to plot the polarization curve.

Figure 3: System start-up from cold state to nominal conditions (test performed on 09/15/2022)

A non-linear Generalized Reduced Gradient (GRG) optimization algorithm has been applied to the equation of the polarization curve and provided a satisfactory fitting with a root mean square error of 10^{-3} , as depicted in Figure 4. The three fitted parameters, summarized in Table 2, were then compared to typical value ranges found for PEM technology under the same operating conditions, demonstrating consistent alignment with existing literature data [4]. To illustrate, Biaku et al. [8] reported solutions on the order of 10^{-4} to 10^{-3} for the anode exchange current density and of 10^{-1} for the cathode exchange current density.

Figure 4: Fitting of the polarization curve at 65°C

Description	Parameter	Value
Anode exchange current density (A/cm^2)	$i_{0,\text{an}}$	$1.34 \cdot 10^{-4}$
Cathode exchange current density (A/cm^2)	$i_{0,\text{cat}}$	$8 \cdot 10^{-1}$
Equivalent ohmic resistance (Ω)	R_{eq}	$3.18 \cdot 10^{-1}$

Table 2: Fitted parameters from the polarization curve equation

The next step of this work will consist in validating the entire model. Once achieved, long-term simulations will be conducted to capture seasonal intermittency, with the goal of defining and testing advanced control strategies and monitoring tools.

2. Experimental results

The same test also served as a benchmark for assessing key performance indicators of the electrolyzer at nominal conditions, including the mean specific consumption at the stack and system levels and the quality of produced hydrogen. An additional test has been performed under dynamic grid conditions and compared to the system baseline performance obtained at nominal conditions and allowed drawing the first outcomes on the impacts of intermittency. The results from these tests are summarized in Table 3.

KPI	Dynamic grid conditions	Steady-state nominal conditions
Stack specific consumption (kWh/Nm ³ H ₂)	3.924	4.334
System specific consumption (kWh/Nm ³ H ₂)	7.786	5.784
Amount of O ₂ in H ₂ (%)	1.058	0.298

Table 3: Performance of the 55 kW PEM electrolyzer under dynamic and steady-state nominal conditions (test performed on 09/15/2022)

Additional dynamic profiles based on grid services and renewable load scenarios will be tested to further refine these first conclusions.

Conclusion

In this paper, a methodology aimed at deepening the level of understanding on intermittency issues was introduced. This approach hinges on the development of a performance model of a system-scale electrolyzer and the implementation of experimental tests designed to evaluate different topologies of intermittent power profiles and deduce relevant outcomes regarding the impacts of intermittency on the performance of electrolyzer systems. Preliminary results from the test campaign have also contributed to the validation of the electrochemical submodel and the calibration of the polarization curve with a high correlation factor. Further tests will be performed in order to validate the entire model and build a strong database on intermittency impacts. This will provide valuable information to develop and test mitigation strategies based on long-term simulations over a large spectrum of intermittent load scenarios.

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